

A SUSTAINABLE WAY FOR ENERGY IN FUTURE AND CHALLENGES FOR SOLAR ENERGY UTILIZATION

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ABSTRACT

This article discusses the transition from a chemical energy base built on fossil fuels to physical energy base built mainly on electricity from renewable sources. This transition is predetermined by laws of physics. Hydrogen is not a new energy, but only an artificial synthetic energy carrier. It has to be fabricated from high grade energy like electricity or natural gas. Before the technology of hydrogen is developed or implemented, it has to compete with high grade energy in the market. Sun energy is by far the largest exploitable resource, providing more energy in one hour to the earth than all the energy consumed by human in an entire year. In view of the intermittency of insolation, if solar energy is to be a major primary energy source, it must be stored and dispatched on demand to the end user. An especially attractive approach is to store-converted energy in form of chemical bonds. Scientific challenges involves with this process in addition to capturing and converting solar energy and then store the energy in form of chemical bonds, producing oxygen from water and reduce fuel such as hydrogen.

KEYWORDS:” Energy Sustainability and Solar Energy Challenges”

INTRODUCTION

The attainment of a sustainable energy in future is one of the most pressing task of mankind with the exhaustion of fossil resources of energy economy will change from a chemical to an electrical base. This transition is one of the physics but not of politics. However proven technology and existing engineering experience are of course useful. Action must be taken first to start a transition which will take many years to complete.

Unfortunately, politics seems to listen to the advice of visionaries, lobby groups and environmental activists, all presenting qualitative arguments, hardly ever based on facts and physics. A sustainable energy in future cannot be founded on shaky arguments, hype and activism, but has to be built on solid grounds of established science and engineering. (Rifkin and Putman, 2002)

Meeting global energy demand in a sustainable fashion will require not only increased energy efficiency and new methods of using existing carbon-based fuels but also a daunting amount of new carbon-neutral energy. (Energy information administration 2005)

THE SUSTAINABLE ENERGY IN FUTURE

There are two postulates to be satisfied to make the energy system sustainable.

1. All energy must come from sustainably managed renewable sources.
2. Energy must be distributed and used with the highest efficiency.

In the context ‘sustainable’ is used in its original meaning. In the late 18th century, the mandate of sustainability was created by the Prussian Forest administration to mean “never take more wood out of a forest than nature can replenish between two harvesting period”. This rule applies to all interactions between man and nature. In the energy area, it involved the harvest of energy supplied as well as the release of reaction products to environment at the other end of the energy chain. Nature’s ability to release or absorb is limiting the use of energy from all sources clearly fossil fuels and nuclear (fusion and fission) energy do not satisfy these enteria on both ends of the energy chain. Resources are finite and the release of geo-carbon dioxide or radioactive waste cannot be absorb by the nature, for example Biomass is not sustainable per second, but its growth and harvest must be managed in a sustainable way like forest in parts of Europe. Also the sustainability of some hydro power projects could be questioned. Artificial lakes are gradually filled with silt and become useless with time. Furthermore, the damage caused by flooding fertile valleys may be in conflict with sustainable mandate.

However, must hydro power, solar energy, wind power, ocean energy or geothermal installations harvest renewable in a sustainable way. Energy obtained from sustainably managed biomass and organic waste complete in the list of renewable. After depletion of fossil and uranium deposits energy must come these sources. There is no other sustainable energy that could possibly contribute substantially to the energy needs of mankind. However the conversion of renewable energy into commercial quantity is not trivial. It will take years to switch from today's fossil-based energy system to a new platform built on physical energy harvested from nature in a sustainable way.

Onset and speed of this transition to sustainability (from chemical to physical) depend on;

- availability of hydro power, wind, sun geothermal heat and biomass.
- climatic condition for harvesting solar wind and biomass.
- topology along shorelines for harvesting ocean energy.
- availability of lands and sites for renewable energy installations.
- proximity of such installation to urban areas.
- established energy efficiency and standards of energy use.
- political will with sound visions.

The transition may also be showed by local availability of fossil resources, existence of convectional power plants or strong business interests.

Countries without fossil resources are already moving towards sustainability and those with rich fossil deposits finally begin to recognize the challenges. There is no global road map to sustainability, but regional solutions are needed to reflect local situations. Road map and international agreements slow the process in lead countries while established energy economy may discourage changes.

RENEWABLE ENERGY AND THE ENERGY MARKET.

For a planned transition from today's to a sustainable energy base one needs to consider the properties of renewable energy supplied by nature. Without any question, the energy demand of mankind can be satisfied from renewable sources. The sun supplies many thousand times our energy needs. However, meteorological fluctuations, variations by climate zones availability of sites, etc need to consider and site-specific solutions must be found. Energy from renewable sources is already competitive in some areas. The number of attractive sites is rapidly increasing with rising oil prices and further development of green energy technologies. Wind energy has become attractive on windy sites of all continents. There is no global distribution problem for energy from renewable sources. Renewable energy is available where people live.

However, with the exception of biomass renewable energy is harvested as physical energy, some as heat, but the vast bulk as electricity. Consider the following compilation:

Solar energy	Photovoltaic	DC Electricity
	Collector	Heating
	Concentrators	AC Electricity
Wind energy		AC Electricity
Hydropower		AC electricity
Ocean energy Wave		AC Electricity
	Tides	AC Electricity
Geothermal	LT heat	Heating
	HT heat	AC Electricity
Biomass	Synthetic	
	LT heat	Heating
	HT heat	AC Electricity
Organic waste Synthetic fuels		
	HT	AC electricity

Today, about 80% of the energy is derived from chemical and 20% from physical sources, the future will see just the opposite if sustainable energy is adopted that is about 80% will be harvested as electricity or low-temperature heat with about 20% being available from organic resources.

A closer look however, reveals that in the future energy supply is much better matched to the energy demand of consumers. People need chemical energy only for food. All other energy services are supplied in a form of physical energy. Motion. Today chemical energy is converted to satisfy these physical energy needs. In future, electricity could be used directly to assure comfort and living standard of people. Fortunately, consumers' needs of energy services are better matched in a sustainable energy than in today's chemical world.

INVERSION OF THE ENERGY SYSTEM

With the end of fossil reserves the era of chemical energy conversion is bound to come to an end. This development this is irreversible. It can only be slowed, but not stopped by politics, energy wars, or the introduction of synthetic energy carriers like hydrogen. We have to face the future and prepare for it.

Today energy system is dominated by chemical carriers like coal, oil and gas. Electricity and transportation energy is derived from chemical energy by thermal power plants, heat engines, or fuel cells. During the last two centuries scientist and engineers have developed fascinating thermal energy conversion devices and related theories. From oil wells to deriving on high ways, much of today's economy is directly related to the conversion of chemical energy of fossil origin into energy services of physical nature.

What does the future looks like? The sustainable energy in future will be dominated perhaps to 80% by electrical energy from renewable sources. Renewable electricity will be transmitted directly to the user via existing and new power lines. Chemical energy must be derived from electricity via existing and new power lines. Chemical energy must derived from electricity e.g. by electrolysis of water. Therefore electricity derived hydrogen is unlikely to be converted back to electricity by thermal power plants or fuels cells. Renewable electricity will gradually replace fossil fuels. Electricity will become the base of our energy system. It does not make sense to continue with the chemical energy technologies by converting good electricity into hydrogen for use in steam power plants.

The inversion of the energy system will affect our entire energy world and change our energy system. Many chemical conversion technologies may become obsolete. Coal oil or gas fired power plants and internal combustion engines will "run out of fuel". Electric heat pumps will become real energy multipliers. Without Carnot losses, the overall efficiency of the energy system may reach 50%. Efficient electrical transmission and appliances will replace in efficient chemical energy conversion and distribution technologies. Green electricity, combined with an efficient energy distribution and use, will become the base of a sustainable energy world. Because of the improved overall efficiency, even a growing demand of the energy services can be satisfied from renewable sources (Bossel 2005).

The transition from chemical to an electrical energy use is too complex to be analyzed in detail. We have to face the need for the changed and to work without fruitless debate about economic consequences. The cost per KWh of future renewable electricity cannot be compared to the present cost of electricity generated by converting coal to electricity in amortized, but inefficient and dirty thermal power plant. Resulting from higher efficiency monthly energy bills may even be lower than that of today. Future options should be compared with each other, not with today's standards. However, as renewable energy itself comes for free, while oil and gas prices will gradually climb with demand and depletion. By this argument investment in optimized and lasting renewable energy equipment should eventually become extremely profitable.

ENERGY STRATEGY OPTIONS

There are two main options for the delivery of sustainable energy to the consumer. Both of them are free of "geocarbon", thus environmentally clean. Both start with renewable electricity and provide energy users with similar energy services. These options differ only with respect to the choice of base energy, chemical and electrical.

At this time the favored and more convenient option is to maintain the chemical energy base. The intent is to replace fossil fuels by synthetic hydrogen and continue the energy business as usual, oil companies become hydrogen suppliers, roadside fuel stations pump hydrogen instead of gasoline, and cars are powered by hydrogen and fuel cells. This option termed "hydrogen economy" can certainly be realized for the necessary technology is available and even an improved one can be developed in time.

The second option is controlled transition from today's chemical to an electrical energy base. Renewable energy is brought to the people in form of electricity. The necessary technology is also available or can be develop upon rapidly. This option, an "electron economy" can certainly be realized.

Both options require some additional research and development. New storage technologies are needed for hydrogen as well as for electrons. But hydrogen infrastructure must be built from scratch while the electric power grids only need a modest extension in most parts of the world. In fact, the electron option may be much closer to today's energy technology and therefore, much easier implemented than the hydrogen option.

In simple terms a "hydrogen economy" has to compete with an "electron economy". Both options deliver renewable electricity to people, but by use of different energy carriers. Winner will be the option with the lower energy losses between energy sources and energy services. The situation is illustrated in figure 1. The competition between hydrogen and electricity is determined by the respective overall energy efficiency between renewable source and the use.

Renewable Electricity to the User

Figure 1: Energy distribution options in a sustainable energy future

THE MYTH OF "HYDROGEN ENERGY"

Hydrogen is promoted as a new source of energy. This is certainly nonsense, to be clear. It is true that hydrogen is the most abundant element of our universe, but it exists only in chemical compounds like water, fossil fuel or organic biomass. Furthermore, the abundance of hydrogen cannot be a sales argument, because hydrogen atoms are not destroyed by their energetic use. The gas is obtained by splitting water with the help of electrical energy into hydrogen and oxygen. The invested energy is later recovered, unfortunately only partially, when hydrogen and oxygen are combined and the original amount of water is restored. Hydrogen is not an energy source but an energy carrier much like water in a hydronic heating system (Rifkin and Putman 2002).

Hydrogen may be extracted from natural gas by steam reforming or from water by electrolysis. In both cases, more energy is needed to liberates hydrogen from its chemical bounds than can ever be recovered by oxidizing the energy carriers for energy release. The equation "hydrogen plus air = energy plus drinking water" reflects simplified views of layman. It seems that the energetic base of hydrogen generation and use are not

properly considered in the ongoing hydrogen debate, where does the energy come from to “Create”. “Hydrogen energy”? (Bossel, Eliasson and Taylor 2003).

From water by electrolysis:

$$\text{electrical energy} + \text{H}_2\text{O} = \text{H}_2\text{-energy} + \frac{1}{2}\text{O}_2$$

$$286\text{KJmol}^{-1} = 286\text{KJmol}^{-1}$$

Reality

130% energy input = 100% H₂-energy + 30% losses.

From neutral gas by reforming

$$\text{neutral gas energy} + \text{heat} + \text{H}_2\text{O} = \text{H}_2\text{-energy} + \text{CO}_2$$

$$890\text{KJmol}^{-1} + 254\text{KJmol}^{-1} = 1,144\text{KJmol}^{-1} (= 4 \times 286\text{KJmol}^{-1})$$

Reality

115% energy input = 100% H₂-energy + 15% losses.

SOLAR ENERGY UTILIZATION.

Solar energy utilization requires (i) solar capture and conversion and (ii) storage. Solar capture and conversion may be accomplished by photovoltaics (pvs). The challenge here is to dramatically reduce the cost per watt of delivered solar electricity. Compared with fossil energy, solar energy is diffused, and hence the material costs must be very inexpensive to make a solar-based process economical. Knowing that the isolation has been striking an area of the earth for a 30 years period, it is relatively simple to calculate the sale price of converted energy that is needed to pay back at least the initial cost that is required to cover that area with the solar energy conversion system. (Solar energy utilization workshop 2005).

In the absence of cost effective storage, solar electricity can never be a primary source of energy for our society diurnal variation in local isolation. In principle, storage of electricity could be obtained using batteries, but at present no battery is inexpensive enough, when amortized over 30 years life time of a solar device, to satisfy the needed cost per W targets for the whole system. A second method is to store the electrical energy mechanically. For instances, electricity could be used to drive turbines to pump water uphill. This approach is relative inexpensive for storing large amount of energy at modest charge and discharge rates, but it is not well matched to being charged and discharged every 24 hours to compensate for the diurnal cycle. Currently, the cheapest method of solar energy capture, conversion and storage is solar thermal technology which costs little for the production of electricity. Advances in this potentially very important approach to solar energy utilization will require new materials for the focusing and thermal capture of energy in sunlight, as well as new thermochemical cycles for producing useful fuel from the captured solar energy. The possibility of integrated capture, conversion, and storage functions makes solar thermal technology an option that should be vigorously pursued to exploit the large untapped solar energy resource for carbon-neutral energy production.

A third method of storage is to borrow the design of nature, in which chemical bonds are broken and formed to produce solar fuel in an artificial photosynthesis process. Photosynthesis itself is relatively inefficient, when measured on a yearly average basis per unit area of insolation. Because the average insolation at a typical midlatitude is 200-300 Wm⁻², the yearly average energy conversion and storage efficiency of the most rapidly growing large area crops is currently less than 0.5%. Whereas biofuels derived from existing plants could provide a potentially significant contribution to liquid fuels for transportation uses (if cellulosic conversion technology

can be successfully developed and deployed economically) increased energy conversion and storage efficiency are highly desirable to remove land area as a serious constraint on the amount of energy that can be obtained from the sun and stored in chemical bonds. One approach is to develop an artificial photosynthetic process with an average efficiency significantly higher than plants or algae. (U.N.D.P 2003).

The primary steps of photosynthesis involve the conversion of sunlight into a “wireless current.” In all cases, to a useful fuel oxygen must be involved, so it can be released into our oxygen-containing atmosphere and use elsewhere as an oxidation reagent for fuel consumption. The reduced fuel could be either hydrogen from water reduction, or organic species such as methanol or methane, that is derived from the fixation of atmospheric CO₂. Recombination of the reduced fuel with released O₂ would then regenerate the original species, closing the cycle in a carbon neutral fashion.

In natural photosynthesis, anodic charge of the wireless current is used at the oxygen-evolving complex to oxidise water to oxygen, with the contaminant release of four protons. The cathodic charge of the wireless current is captured by photosystem I to reduce the protons to “hydrogen” with the reduced hydrogen equivalents stored through the conversion of NADP to NADPH. Thus, the overall primary events of photosynthesis store sunlight by the rearrangement of the chemical bonds of water, to form oxygen and nature’s form of hydrogen.

An artificial photosynthesis could be realised by spatially separating solid-state or molecular water reduction and oxidation catalysts and connecting them to a light collection and charge separation system. In one such construct, the spatially separated electron-hole pairs provided by a photovoltaic assembly based on a solid-state junction, on either the macroscale or the nanoscale, are captured by the catalysts, and the energy is stored in the bond rearrangement of water to H₂ and O₂. Other concepts involve more intimate integration of the charge separation and chemical bond-forming functions, to avoid costs and system constraints associated with electrical contacts, wires, inverters, etc, involved with converting 1eV photon into 1eV chemical bonds through electricity as a discrete intermediary.

THE BASIC SCIENCE NEEDS FOR PHOTOVOLTAICS

One of the key issues in solar capture and conversion is how to separate charge efficiently from microscopic distances without using expensive, highly pure, semiconductor materials. This effort requires the development of new chemical and materials methods to make polycrystalline and nanocrystalline semiconductors perform as if they were expensive single crystals. Numerous research approaches are being pursued in this area (Energy Utilization Workshop 2005). Material consisting of a network of interpenetrating regions can facilitate effective charge separation and collection, thus relaxing the usual constraint in which the photogenerated carriers must exist long enough to traverse the entire distance of the cell-present photon conversion devices based on a single-band gap absorber, including semiconductor PV, have a theoretical thermodynamic conversion efficiency of 32% in unconcentrated sunlight. However, the conversion efficiency can be increased, in principle to 45-65% if carrier thermalization can be prevented (by overcoming the so-called Shockley-Queisser limit).

In addition to making evolutionary changes to existing PV technologies, new materials for future generation PVs are needed. Building upon the recent success in developing efficient molecular organic PVs and the recent advances in the controlled assembly of hybrid organic/inorganic nanostructures, organic and hybrid PV cells could possibly exceed 10% energy conversion efficiency, while offering a potentially inexpensive manufacturing paradigm. (e.g. casting from emulsions, printing and use of flexible substrates for production of large-area thin-film cells; Shabeen, Ginley and Jobbour 2005). To guide the PV nanostructure assembly, biologically derived and/or genetically engineered systems might be used to control the crystal structure, phase orientation and nanostructural regularity of inorganic materials.

THE BASIC NEEDS FOR SOLAR FUELS.

As described above, an important storage approach involves conversion of the energy captured in the charge-separated states or a solar captured and conversion system into chemical bonds. Water splitting is an example of a more general conversion to a solar fuel cycle that involves evolution of oxygen as one component and formation of a reduced fuel as the other. Unexplored basic science issues are immediately confronted when the problem is posed in the simplest chemistry framework.

The overall transformation is multielectron process promoted by photocatalyst and light. Elucidation of the fundamental principle of single electron-transfer reactions represented such as important milestone in chemistry that two noble prizes were awarded for such work(Marcus 1993 and Taube 1984). Although dramatic advances have occurred in our understanding of single electron-transfer reactions, especially those in biology (Gray and Winkler 2005), a similar level of understand of multielectron redox reaction has yet to be realised. Moreover, to ensure charged neutrality in the system, proton transfer must accompany electron transfer (i.e, proton-coupled electron transfer; Cukier and Nocera 1998); hence, electron and proton inventories, both need to be managed (Chang *et al* 2004). Water splitting additionally presents sizable thermodynamic and kinetic barriers to making and breaking the bonds required to facilitate the desired chemical reactions. This is especially pertinent to the water-splitting problem, because the byproduct of water activation at the catalyst, Whether molecular or solid, will invariably yield species that have strong metal-oxygen bonds.To close a catalytic cycle, these stable bond need to be activated by the captured solar energy either directly or indirectly.More generally, the activation of all small molecules of consequences to carbon-neutral solar energy storage, including CO₂, O₂and H₂O, share the reaction commonalities of bond-making and breaking processes that require multielectron transfer coupled to photon transfer.

FROM NOW TO ENERGY SUSTAINABILITY IN FUTURE.

Unless caused by political shocks, war or OPEC dicision changes in the energy sector proceed slowly.But trend are apparent and ongoing, perhaps too small to be noticed on the yearly energy statistics, but accumulating changes over the years.They are caused by supply and demand,by new energy technologies, by the emergence of powerfull economies, by defletion of resouces by air quality legislation and similar developments.The growth demand and declinig resources have led to rising energy prices with the following noticable effects.

In the stationary sector, the demand of heating fuels is declining it is as a result of;

- improved thermal insulation of buildings.
- more efficient –HVAC appliances
- use of biofuels like; wood chips and pellets.
- use of electricity for direct heating and heat pumps.

In the mobile sector the total fuel consumption is still growing as a result of an increasing number of more and powerful cars on the road. However, the fuel consumption expressed in passengers mile per gallon is declining as a result of;

- improved efficiency of IC engines
- introduction of hybrid electric vehicles.
- substitution of fossil fuels by synthetic hydrocarbon or biogas.
- use of small battery-electric cars and scooters for commuting.

The overall efficiency of our energy is increased by

- higher conversion efficiency of power plants or IC engines.
- higher efficiency of electrical energy distribution system.
- rising energy awareness and change in consumer behavior,
- growing supply of electricity from renewable resourses .

CONCLUSION.

For the attainment of a sustainable energy in future the present energy system has to undergo significant changes,not just minor adaptations or modifications. The key point is the transition from a chemical energy base built on fossils fuels to physical energy base built mainly on electricity from renewable sources. This transition is predetermined by the laws of physics.

It cannot be avoided or significantly delayed by politics. However, the transition will proceed more smoothly,if all players agreed to moved in the same direction. Without the slightest doubt,the technology for a hydrogen economy exist or can be developed in reasonable time. Also hydrogen is an appropriate energy carrier for

particular niche applications, or it may become an important medium for electricity storage with reversible fuels cells.

The solar energy resource far exceeds what can possibly be envisioned as a level of human consumption necessary to support even the most technologically advanced society. However to be a material contribution to primary energy supply, solar energy must be captured, converted and stored to overcome the diurnal cycle and the intermittency of the terrestrial solar resources. Arguably the most attractive method for this energy conversion and storage in a form of chemical bonds, by production of cheap solar fuel. Significant advances in the basic science, however are needed for this technology to attain its full potential.

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